

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021
hash://md5/166a4626482ee60eb982827eff29ace1

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021`, has fingerprint `hash://md5/166a4626482ee60eb982827eff29ace1`, is 8.91MiB in size and contains 5,566 interactions with 3 unique types of associations (e.g., `hasParasite`) between 2,032 primary taxa (e.g., *Bembidion Latreille, 1802*) and 716 associated taxa (e.g., *Laboulbenia vulgaris Peyr.*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Pozsgai, G., Ben Fekih, I., Kohnen, M.V. et al. Associations between carabid beetles and fungi in the light of 200 years of published literature. *Sci Data* 8, 294 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01072-w> <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021/archive/35dc44c4534694572fad78f0a4c2026-02-05T00:16:48.735Z> hash://md5/166a4626482ee60eb982827eff29ace1

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like `grep`, `mlr`, `tail` and `head`.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.5
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 8.91MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](https://github.com/possgai/check-data.sh). See also GitHub and Codeberg.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2021`, has fingerprint hash: `//md5/166a4626482ee60eb982827eff29ace1`, is 8.91MiB in size and contains 5,566 interactions with 3 unique types of associations (e.g., `hasParasite`) between 2,032 primary taxa (e.g., *Bembidion Latreille, 1802*) and 716 associated taxa (e.g., *Laboulbenia vulgaris Peyr.*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Trichognatha marginipennis Latreille, 1829	hasParasite	Laboulbenia trichognathi Thaxt.	(article?) {spegazzini1917amnhnba, title = {Re- visi<U+03CC>n de las {Laboulbeniales} {Argentinias}}, volume = {29}, number = {9}, journal = {Anales del Museo Nacional de Historia Natural de Buenos Aires}, author = {Spegazzini, Carlos}, year = {1917}, keywords = {icle}, pages = {445-688}, }

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Abacetus Dejean, 1828	hasParasite	Laboulbenia anoplogeniei Thaxt.	(article?) {haelewaters2015m, title = {New and interesting {Laboulbeniales} from southern and southeastern {Asia}}, volume = {129}, issn = {00934666, 21548889}, url = {http://openurl.ingenta.com/content/xref?genre= 4666&volume=129&issue=2&spage=439}, doi = {10.5248/129.439}, abstract = {Two new species of Laboulbenia from the Philippines are described and illustrated: Laboulbenia erotylidarum on an erotylid beetle (Coleoptera, Erotylidae) and Laboulbenia poplitea on Craspedophorus sp. (Coleoptera, Carabidae). In addition, we present ten new records of Laboulbeniales from several countries in southern and southeastern Asia on coleopteran hosts. These are Blasticomyces lispini from Borneo (Indonesia), Cantharomyces orientalis from the Philippines, Dimeromyces rugosus on Leiochrodes sp. from Sumatra (Indonesia),

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Acupalpus exiguus Dejean, 1829	hasParasite	Rhachomyces lasiophorus (Thaxt.) Thaxt.	(article?) {dekesela.rammeloo1991bjb, title = {Checklist of the {Laboulbeniales} ({Ascomycetes}) of {Belgium}.}, volume = {124}, number = {2}, journal = {Belgian Journal of Botany}, author = {De Kesel, André and Rammeloo, J}, year = {1991}, keywords = {laboulbeniales}, pages = {204–214}, } (article?) {briedis1932ahbul, title = {Laboulbeniaceae in {Latvia}}, volume = {7}, number = {1-3}, journal = {Acta Horti Botanici Universitatis Latviensis}, author = {Briedis, A}, year = {1932}, pages = {131–134}, }
Patrobus excavatus (Paykull, 1790)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia brachiata Thaxt.	(article?) {briedis1932ahbul, title = {Laboulbeniaceae in {Latvia}}, volume = {7}, number = {1-3}, journal = {Acta Horti Botanici Universitatis Latviensis}, author = {Briedis, A}, year = {1932}, pages = {131–134}, }

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
hasParasite	5442
hasPathogen	62
interactsWith	62

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Bembidion Latreille, 1802	70
Harpalus affinis (Schrank, 1781)	47
Pterostichus melanarius (Illiger, 1798)	41
Harpalus Latreille, 1802	38
Brachinus Weber, 1801	38
Galerita Fabricius, 1801	32
Chlaenius Bonelli, 1810	31
Trechus de Clairville, 1806	31
Pterostichus nigrita (Paykull, 1790)	30
Brachinus crepitans (Linnaeus, 1758)	29
Dyschirius globosus (Herbst, 1784)	27
Calathus melanocephalus (Linnaeus, 1758)	27
Clivina Latreille, 1802	26
Pterostichus Bonelli, 1810	26
Brachinus explodens Duftschmid, 1812	25
Clivina fossor (Linnaeus, 1758)	25
Tachys Dejean, 1821	25
Pterostichus strenuus (Panzer, 1796)	23
Bradycellus Erichson, 1837	23

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Laboulbenia vulgaris Peyr.	600
Laboulbenia flagellata Peyr.	404
Laboulbenia Mont. & C.P.Robin	241
Laboulbenia pedicellata Thaxt.	241
Laboulbenia rougetii Mont. & C.P.Robin	139
Laboulbenia polyphaga Thaxt.	125
Misgomyces dyschirii Thaxt.	109
Laboulbenia ophoni Thaxt.	100
Laboulbenia proliferans Thaxt.	86
Laboulbenia pseudomasei Thaxt.	86
Laboulbenia subterranea Thaxt.	74
Laboulbenia casnoniae Thaxt.	66
Laboulbenia coneglanensis Speg.	65
Laboulbenia pterostichi Thaxt.	61
Laboulbenia argutoris Cépède & F.Picard	60

targetTaxonName	count
Laboulbenia nebriae Peyr.	60
Laboulbenia filifera Thaxt.	59
Laboulbenia anoplogenii Thaxt.	56
Laboulbenia luxurians Peyr.	53

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Clivina fossor (Linnaeus, 1758)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia clivinalis Thaxt.	21
Bembidion Latreille, 1802	hasParasite	Laboulbenia vulgaris Peyr.	17
Bembidion tetracolum Say, 1823	hasParasite	Laboulbenia vulgaris Peyr.	17
Brachinus crepitans (Linnaeus, 1758)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia rougetii Mont. & C.P.Robin	16
Trechus de Clairville, 1806	hasParasite	Rhachomyces canariensis Thaxt.	16
Platynus assimilis (Paykull, 1790)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia flagellata Peyr.	14
Pterostichus strenuus (Panzer, 1796)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia argutoris Cépède & F.Picard	14
Dyschirius globosus (Herbst, 1784)	hasParasite	Misgomyces dyschirii Thaxt.	14
Bembidion ustulatum (Duftschmid, 1812)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia vulgaris Peyr.	14
Pterostichus nigrita (Paykull, 1790)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia pseudomasei Thaxt.	13
Chlaenius vestitus (Paykull, 1790)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia Mont. & C.P.Robin	13

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Leistus ferrugineus (Linnaeus, 1758)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia leisti J.Siemaszko & Siemaszko	12
Dyschirius globosus (Herbst, 1784)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia pedicellata Thaxt.	12
Calathus melanocephalus (Linnaeus, 1758)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia polyphaga Thaxt.	12
Bembidion pallidipenne (Illiger, 1802)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia vulgaris Peyr.	12
Diachromus germanus (Linnaeus, 1758)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia melanaria Thaxt.	12
Agonum muelleri (Herbst, 1784)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia flagellata Peyr.	11
Clivina collaris (Herbst, 1784)	hasParasite	Laboulbenia clivinalis Thaxt.	11
Brachinus explodens Duftschmid, 1812	hasParasite	Laboulbenia rougetii Mont. & C.P.Robin	11

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.c

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

[sv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at [indexed-interactions.gpkg](#) for point data and [indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg](#) for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at [GloBI website](#), by opening a [GitHub issue](#), or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the [GloBI website](#).

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abacetus amaroides	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Abacetus amaroides
Abacetus audax	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Abacetus audax
Abacetus pubescens	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Abacetus pubescens
Abacetus submetallicus	HAS_ACCEPTED	col	Abacetus submetallicus

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	135
col	genus	248
col	species	2321
col	subgenus	19
col	subspecies	69
col	subtribe	1
discoverlife	NA	2748
gbif	NA	65
gbif	family	1
gbif	genus	298
gbif	species	2357
gbif	subspecies	37
itis	NA	2393
itis	genus	103
itis	species	247
itis	subgenus	4
itis	subspecies	1
mdd	NA	2748
ncbi	NA	1808
ncbi	genus	219
ncbi	species	703
ncbi	subgenus	22
ncbi	subspecies	1
pbdb	NA	2575
pbdb	genus	70
pbdb	species	101

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	subgenus	1
pbdb	subtribe	1
pbdb	tribe	1
tpt	NA	2748
wfo	NA	2743
wfo	genus	4
wfo	species	1
worms	NA	2636
worms	genus	66
worms	species	44
worms	subgenus	2

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2150
col	SYNONYM_OF	688
col	NONE	135
discoverlife	NONE	2759
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2261
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	658
gbif	NONE	65
itis	NONE	2399
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	310
itis	SYNONYM_OF	51
mdd	NONE	2759
ncbi	NONE	1808
ncbi	SAME_AS	896
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	60
pbdb	NONE	2583
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	46
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	133
tpt	NONE	2759
wfo	NONE	2754
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	3
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	2

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
worms	NONE	2646
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	104
worms	SYNONYM_OF	11

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdc	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-02-05T02:41:15Z	note	missing interaction type
2026-02-05T02:41:15Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/pozsgai2026

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-02-05T02:41:15Z	summary	5566 interaction(s)
2026-02-05T02:41:15Z	summary	1 note(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
missing interaction type	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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⁵At time of writing (2026-02-05) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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